

Transport Equity in Dockless Bike-Sharing: Behavioral Clustering and Socioeconomic Patterns in Shenzhen

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Summary

Dockless bike-sharing systems promise more equitable urban mobility. However, their market-driven deployment may reinforce inequities in service provision. Using ~123 million trip records from Shenzhen, this study examines how socio-economic characteristics relate to bike-sharing behavior. Regression results show that lower education levels and housing overcrowding are associated with reduced usage. A behavioral clustering analysis identifies five distinct user patterns. Cross-tabulation further reveals that advantaged areas concentrate frequent, habitual users, while disadvantaged areas are dominated by occasional, longer-distance users. Overall, the findings confirm associations between behavioral patterns and socio-economic characteristics, highlighting inequities within market-driven bike-sharing deployment.

KEYWORDS: transport equity, bike-sharing system, socioeconomic patterns, user behavior

1. Introduction

Dockless bike-sharing systems have rapidly expanded across Chinese cities, promoted as equitable urban mobility solutions with flexible, station-free design and pay-per-use model. However, market-driven deployment concentrates bikes in high-demand areas to maximize profits, potentially reinforcing existing urban socioeconomic divisions (Chen et al., 2020). Previous research confirms spatial inequities, with higher usage in wealthier, central areas (Hosford and Winters, 2018; Zhou and Schwanen, 2024). While most studies focus on overall usage levels, the question of whether users from different socioeconomic backgrounds also exhibit different behavioral patterns remains underexplored.

This study examines socioeconomic-behavior relationships in Shenzhen through two questions: Do socioeconomic factors influence bike-sharing usage? And do users from different socioeconomic contexts exhibit different usage patterns? Understanding these relationships is crucial for assessing whether shared mobility systems enhance equity or reinforce inequities (Goodman and Cheshire, 2014). We analyze bike-sharing trip records during May–July 2021 in Shenzhen. Through regression analysis and behavioral clustering, our findings reveal associations between socioeconomic characteristics and both usage levels and behavioral patterns.

2. Data and Methods

2.1 Data

This study uses Shenzhen dockless bike-sharing trip records from May–July 2021 (123 million trips; 7.3 million users). Analyses use H3, a hexagonal hierarchical spatial indexing system, at resolution 10 (approximately 75m edge length) as the spatial unit of analysis. User-level behavioral variables capture

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temporal, spatial, and usage patterns. Socioeconomic data is population-weighted and distributed to hexagons through areal interpolation. Additional variables include demographic and land use composition. Table 1 summarises the descriptive statistics for all variables.

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics

Section	Data	Mean	Std	Min	Median	Max
Behavioral	Active days	9.223	15.757	1.0	2.0	92.0
	Trips per day	1.436	0.867	1.0	1.0	43.588
	Distance (km)	1.334	1.57	0.001	0.954	73.732
	Duration (min)	13.016	12.26	0.017	9.917	253.533
	Speed (km/h)	6.584	4.199	1.0	6.125	49.998
	Repeat ratio	0.107	0.198	0.0	0.0	0.994
	Weekday ratio	0.661	0.359	0.0	0.75	1.0
	Peak-hour concentration	0.591	0.321	0.05	0.5	1.0
	Unique origins	7.864	15.659	1.0	3.0	1124.0
Socio economic	Educational disadvantage (z score)	-0.0	1.0	-3.044	0.245	1.296
	Housing crowding (z score)	-0.0	1.0	-2.743	0.184	2.091
	Nonlocal population index (z score)	-0.0	1.0	-3.531	0.067	1.392
Demo graphic	Population density (per km ²)	8901.9 15	7720.05 0	72.126	7063.47 9	64029.99 5
Land use	Residential land share	0.154	0.329	0.0	0.0	1.0
	Commercial land share	0.049	0.191	0.0	0.0	1.0
	Industrial land share	0.127	0.308	0.0	0.0	1.0
	Public service land share	0.121	0.296	0.0	0.0	1.0
	Transportation land share	0.011	0.099	0.0	0.0	1.0
Trip Count	Origin count	901.415	4013.341	0.0	2.0	212122.0

2.2 Linear Regression Analysis

We employ Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression with log-transformed origin count as the dependent variable, following Li et al. (2025). Independent variables include demographics, land use and socioeconomic variables (z-scored). We report HC3 robust standard errors and check multicollinearity using Variance Inflation Factor (VIF), with all values below 2..

2.3 K-means Clustering

We apply K-means clustering to nine user-level behavioral dimensions (El Mahrsi et al., 2017), using clustergram visualisation (Schonlau, 2004) to determine the optimal number of clusters. The clustergram tracks cluster centroid evolution as K increases (Figure 1). It indicates K=5 as optimal, where centroids are well-separated with the most distinct behavioral patterns. The five resulting groups range from light occasional use to highly active habitual engagement.

Each user is then assigned to their most frequent origin hexagon as their area of residence. Cross-tabulation of clusters with socioeconomic quintiles examines associations between behavioral patterns and socioeconomic context.

Figure 1 Clustergram visualisation of K-means clustering (K=2 to 10)

3. Results

3.1 Socioeconomic Factors and Bike-Sharing Demand

To explore the relationship between socioeconomic characteristics and bike-sharing usage in Shenzhen, we first employ linear regression analysis. The model achieves an R^2 of 0.449 across 133,604 hexagonal cells (Table 2), with all variables significant at $p < 0.001$ (Table 3). Multicollinearity is assessed through VIF values, all below 2 (Table 4).

Table 2 Model information

N	R2	Adj. R ²	Covariance
133604	0.449	0.449	HC3

Table 3 OLS regression results

Variable	Coef.	Std. Err.	t/z	P> t	CI 2.5%	CI 97.5%
Intercept	2.452	0.006	411.364	0.000	2.440	2.463
Population density	1.298	0.009	141.125	0.000	1.280	1.316
Residential land share	0.648	0.007	86.497	0.000	0.633	0.662
Commercial land share	0.638	0.008	83.887	0.000	0.623	0.653
Industrial land share	0.426	0.006	65.846	0.000	0.413	0.438
Public service land share	0.432	0.007	59.354	0.000	0.417	0.446
Transportation land share	0.126	0.006	22.227	0.000	0.115	0.137

Educational disadvantage (z)	-0.372	0.008	-44.404	0.000	-0.388	-0.355
Housing crowding (z)	-0.201	0.006	-32.912	0.000	-0.213	-0.189

Table 4 Multicollinearity check (VIF)

Variable	VIF
Population Density	1.613
Educational Disadvantage Index	1.593
House Crowding Index	1.334
Residential Land share	1.265
Industrial Land share	1.197
Public Service Land share	1.175
Commercial Land share	1.132
Transportation Land share	1.022

Figure 2 Standardized regression coefficients for bike-sharing usage

As shown in Figure 2, population density is the strongest positive predictor ($\beta = 1.298$). Land-use composition is also positively associated with demand, with the largest effects for residential and commercial land shares.

More importantly, socioeconomic variables reveal important disparities. Educational disadvantage and housing crowding both show significant negative associations with the trip count. This suggests that lower usage in areas with lower education levels and more overcrowded housing, even after accounting for population density and land use patterns. However, these overall patterns do not reveal whether users from different socioeconomic contexts also exhibit different usage behaviors. To explore this dimension, we first identify typical behavioral patterns through clustering analysis.

3.2 Distinct User Behavioral Patterns

K-means clustering identifies five user groups with different engagement levels in the bike-sharing system (Figure 3). The distribution of users and trip counts across different clusters reveals significant

variations in usage intensity.

Cluster 0 (Light & Occasional) contains the largest share of users (43.0%) but contributes only 15.6% of trips. These users exhibit low usage frequency and flexible patterns, with few active days and scattered temporal distribution, reflecting minimal system engagement.

Cluster 1 (Weekday dominant) shows strong weekday preference with trips in fixed time periods, indicating regular schedules.

Cluster 2 (Active & High-Repeat) represents 15.3% of users but generates 62.8% of all trips. With 34 median active days and high location repeat rates, they form the system's core user base, deeply integrated into daily mobility.

Cluster 3 (High-Freq & Multi-Origin) demonstrates exploratory behavior with extensive spatial coverage and flexible timing, exhibiting diverse activity patterns across the city.

Cluster 4 (Long-Distance & High-Speed) comprises occasional users making notably longer trips at higher speeds, representing infrequent use for specific long-distance purposes.

Figure 4 maps the spatial distribution of user origins by cluster. It shows that these behaviors concentrate primarily in southern and central urban core areas of Shenzhen, while Clusters 0 and 4 notably extend to northeastern districts, indicating different spatial coverage. These geographic patterns raise a question: are these behavioral differences randomly distributed across socioeconomic contexts, or do they relate to users' socioeconomic characteristics?

Figure 3 User cluster behavioral profiles (K=5)

Origin Distribution by Cluster

Figure 4 Spatial distribution of user origins by cluster

3.3 Behavioral Patterns and Socioeconomic Context

To explore this association, we cross-tabulate user clusters with educational disadvantage and housing crowding quintiles.

As Figure 5 shows, Cluster 2 (Active & High-Repeat users) concentrates notably in advantaged areas and declines steadily toward disadvantaged quintiles. Cluster 3 (High-Freq & Multi-Origin) shows a

similar advantaged concentration, whereas Cluster 1 (Weekday dominant) remains relatively stable across contexts. In contrast, Cluster 4 (Long-Distance & High-Speed users) shows significantly higher proportion in disadvantaged areas characterized by lower education levels and greater housing crowding. Cluster 0 (Light & Occasional users) also exhibits moderate increase toward disadvantaged contexts.

Behavioral patterns further reveal usage-socioeconomic associations. Advantaged areas demonstrate dense, regular engagement with the system, while disadvantaged areas exhibit sporadic, long-distance usage patterns. Combined with regression results, these patterns reveal that inequity reflects not only in usage levels but also in usage patterns—different contexts shape distinct engagement patterns.

User Cluster Distribution Across Equity Levels

Figure 5 User cluster distribution across socioeconomic quintiles

4. Discussion and Conclusion

Our analysis reveals socioeconomic inequity operates at multiple levels in both volume and patterns. Disadvantaged areas show lower usage and different behaviors, with more occasional, long-distance users versus the frequent, habitual users in advantaged neighborhoods. These results suggest that market-driven deployment risks reinforcing inequities by prioritising high-demand areas. While bike sharing schemes are a fundamental tool for sustainability transitions, recognising and addressing heterogeneity in behavioural patterns is essential for fostering more equitable behavioural change.

This study has limitations. First, we assign users to socioeconomic contexts based on their most frequent origin hexagon as the residential area, without knowing actual travel distances. Second, due to data limitations, our analysis captures a single time period. Longitudinal analysis could reveal temporal evolution of these patterns (Kolkowski et al., 2023). Future research could integrate built environment data, such as points of interest, road network density and public transit accessibility (Moro et al., 2021), to examine how infrastructure interacts with socioeconomic factors to jointly shape usage patterns.

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Biographies

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